

Myth: AI understands me, but I can't understand it

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Everyone can and should understand how AI works, so that—rather than be intimidated or misled by algorithmic decision-making—we can contribute multiple perspectives to designing and implementing the systems that impact us all differently.

Myth

AI understands me, but I can't understand it.

AI is NOT smarter than us. AI should be understandable and accessible.

Watch the talk

iframe

Material

Folien der Präsentation

SCHLÜSSELLITERATUR

Crawford, K. & Paglen, T. (2019, September 19). *Excavating AI: The Politics of Images in Machine Learning Training Sets*.

Timnit Gebru. (2021, April 14). *The Hierarchy of Knowledge in Machine Learning & Related Fields and Its Consequences*.

Zubarev, V. (2018, November 21). *Machine Learning for Everyone*.

ZUSATZLITERATUR

Griffith, C. (2017). *Visualizing Algorithms*.

Kogan, G. (n.d.). *Neural networks*. Retrieved 18 May 2021.

McPherson, T., & Parham, M. (2019, October 24). *'What is a Feminist Lab?'* *Symposium*.

UNICORN IN THE FIELD

Algorithmic Justice League

Color Coded LA

Data Nutrition Project

School of Machines, Making, & Make-Believe

About the author

Sarah Ciston (she/they) is a Virtual Fellow at the Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society, and a Mellon Fellow and PhD Candidate in Media Arts + Practice at University of Southern California. Their research investigates how to bring intersectionality to artificial intelligence by employing queer, feminist, and anti-racist ethics and tactics. They lead Creative Code Collective—a student community for co-learning programming using approachable, interdisciplinary strategies. Their projects include a machine-learning interface that ‘rewrites’ the inner critic and a chatbot that explains feminism to online misogynists. They are currently developing a library of digital-print zines on Intersectional AI.

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Why, AI?

This post is part of our project “Why, AI?”. It is a learning space which helps you to find out more about the myths and truths surrounding automation, algorithms, society and ourselves. It is continuously being filled with new contributions.

[Explore all myths](#)